

Home-School Partnership in Relation to Reading Skills of Learners

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Abstract. The current study delves into exploring the influence of home-school partnerships in improving learners' reading skills. In this study, the researcher selected 120 public elementary school teachers in Bangoy District, Davao City, as the respondents of the study. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. A non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Moment Product Correlation, and multiple linear regression analysis. The study found a significant relationship between home-school partnerships and learners' reading skills, with parental involvement in school and time spent with students emerging as key predictors. Further, correlation analysis enhancing teaching strategies demonstrated a significant relationship between home-school partnerships and learners' reading skills in Bangoy District in Davao City. Evidently, regression analysis proved that home-school partnerships in terms of time students spend with their parents and parents' involvement in school were significant predictors of learners' reading skills in Bangoy District in Davao City. In other words, home-school partnership influences learners' reading skills in Bangoy District in Davao City. Thus, the researcher recommends that other researchers conduct an explanatory study on the mediating factors that cause the relationship between home-school partnership and the reading skills of learners in Bangoy District in Davao City in a larger context may be conducted.

KEY WORDS

1. Home-school partnership
2. Reading skills of learners
3. Teaching English

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1. Introduction

Parents, teachers, and students play a critical role in establishing as well as maintaining the home-school partnership. The contribution of each stakeholder is very important for the desired outcome of school-family partnerships. The parent's role is very important in decision-making at the school level, in collaborating with the community for additional support and resources, and in establishing new learning opportunities for children. Learners' role is also very important in school-family partnerships. Senior students can help in parent-teacher meetings and intervention planning between home and school. Moreover, teachers can maintain regular contact with parents through individualized educational planning meetings, daily report cards,

and notebooks, obtaining information from parents, giving information to them, summarizing the information exchanged, and planning a time for follow-up. As Bailey (2017) highlighted, home-school partnership is a term that describes any support a student receives from a guardian, family, or other mature influence in their home life. According to Antipkina and Ludlow (2020), parental involvement in school is a continuum of parenting behaviors ranging from those representing lower and higher levels of involvement. Punter, Glas, and Meelissen (2016) also noted that home-school partnerships are focused on involvement at home or the parent's behavior towards school life and practicing activities related to school learning with their children at home, involvement with the school or the school-based involvement associated with parents' various forms of participation in the schools' activities, or acknowledge both places for the analysis of involvement behaviors and activities or the home school communication, such as parents interacting with teachers. Previous studies indicated that home and school partnership parental academic support and reading motivation among students. For instance, the study conducted by Ntekane (2018) revealed that a good connection with parents also helps students to feel more comfortable and happier with the quality of education. Hence, it can even motivate those who did not finish their education to continue it. Wang and Sheikh-Khalil (2014) also reported that parental academic support is associated with GPA positively through enhancing educational engagement, while Jung and Zhang (2016) found indirect effects of parental involvement on academic achievement through educational aspiration. Likewise, Tan, Lyu, and Peng (2019) noted that students whose parents were involved in checking their homework showed higher achievement than students whose parents were not involved in checking homework. Parental academic support influences students'

success in different learning areas. Learners who receive sufficient support from their families are more frequently engaged in class and have higher levels of academic achievement. Therefore, this study will bridge the current gap in the literature. This paper will look into the necessary and relevant details of our adolescent readers today in terms of parental academic support and their relationship with their reading motivation and performance, thus providing valuable information into the prediction of students' reading motivation and parental academic support in the basic education context as well as the integration of learners' reading motivation in the curriculum. Meanwhile, Brown et al. (2016) demonstrated that a lack of interest in reading and low engagement in academic reading remains a perennial concern among adolescent students worldwide. According to Park and Kim (2016), adverse reading behaviors such as displeasure and boredom are demonstrated when reading academic materials. This indicates that many collegiate students do not consider academic reading to be an enjoyable activity. Likewise, Ullah and Fatema (2014) indicated that most students in different parts of the world lose interest in reading classes because classes are teacher-centered in which teachers tell students the meaning of difficult words, actively control the classroom activities and dominate the classes. This creates impediments to learners' acquiring knowledge and success in the practical field. In the Philippines, Bustamante and Dequito (2018) reported that the NAT results of elementary and high school students showed a declining achievement level. The Mean Percentage Score (MPS) of students dropped from the school year 2007-2008, which posted an MPS of 49.26 percent to 47.40 percent in 2008-2009, and down to 46.30 percent in 2009-10. Indeed, it was emphasized that the reason for such poor performance in NAT is the students' reading problems. Moreover, Gunobgunob-Mirasol (2019) mentioned that the reading motivation

of Filipino students seemed to decline as they approached higher learning and that reading motivation can be associated with the low performance of the students in English subject and other related subject areas. In the Davao region, the report of Orbeta and Decano (2019) indicated that learners in public schools need help with reading, especially those subjects that use the English language as a medium of instruction. Evidence showed that the learners obtained only an overall mean rating of 65.02 percent, considered a failing mark in national passing identified to be 75 percent and above. Likewise, in the researcher's community, it was found that few students have less interest in reading, as indicated by their low performance in subjects that required extensive reading, such as book reports. Consequently, these scenarios have prompted the researcher to embark on this study. The results of this investigation will definitely provide a greater understanding of how to improve the motivation of the learners at the elementary school level to read in the language instruction of the teachers of English. However, although previous investigations indicated the effectiveness of home-school partnerships with parents on the reading interest of the pupils, much of the research on reading interest has involved pupils at the early childhood level; there is limited research at the elementary school level, especially in public schools. Therefore, there is a need for more excellent studies in this area. Thus, in this context, the researcher felt the need to fill in the research gap by conducting a study in the Philippine context, particularly in the Bangoy District, Davao City, using a quantitative research design. Specifically, the researcher used a causal-comparative approach to better understand the effectiveness of home-school partnerships on the pupils' reading skills, which is found to be scarce.

1.1. *Review of Significant Literature—*

1.1.1. *Home-School Partnership—*Cadosales et al. (2017) defined home-school partner-

ship as parents' emotional and physical presence during students' academic needs. Durisic and Bunijevac (2017) supported this, emphasizing its role in boosting student self-esteem and achievement. Antipkina and Ludlow (2020) highlighted a range of parental involvement levels, from home learning activities to school participation, while Punter, Glas, and Meelissen (2016) discussed the importance of home-school communication. Parental support, both at home and school, improves student motivation, behavior, and academic performance (Chen, 2021; Mata, Pedro, Peixoto, 2018). Hedenbro and Rydelius (2019) noted a reduction in absenteeism with improved communication, and Boonk et al. (2018) added that parental involvement fosters a positive learning environment. Pineda et al. (2018) and Dotterer and Wehrspann (2016) echoed the benefits of parental engagement for both parents and teachers, including improved communication and appreciation.

1.1.2. *Time Spent with Parents—*Quality time spent on academic tasks is crucial (Cadosales et al., 2017). Garcia and Thornton (2014) noted that parental engagement leads to a lifelong love of learning, while Thill (2017) emphasized the positive impact of homework supervision on academic achievement. Similarly, Antipkina and Ludlow (2020) linked homework checking to higher student performance, and Tan, Lyu, and Peng (2019) reiterated the importance of parental involvement in homework completion.

1.1.3. *Parental Involvement in School—*Parental involvement in school activities, such as parent-teacher conferences, leads to better academic performance (Child Trends, 2013). Miles (2016) and Mwirichia (2013) explained that active involvement in decision-making and school events enriches academic achievement, reduces absenteeism, and fosters positive behavior. Alimohammadi et al. (2017) and Liu, Sulaimani, and Henning (2020) highlighted the

benefits of participation in school-based activities, including improved communication and support.

1.1.4. Discipline and Student Behavior—Cadosales et al. (2017) suggested that the way parents discipline their children influences their school behavior. Positive reinforcement fosters a conducive learning environment (Zouzou, 2015; Korpershoek et al., 2014), while Yildiz (2017) noted that consistent reinforcement enhances student behavior and engagement.

1.1.5. Reading Skills—Reading skills involve comprehension, interpretation, and decoding of text (Muliati, 2017). Motivation plays a significant role in reading achievement (Hussain, Salam, Farid, 2020). Alhamdu (2015) and Carroll and Fox (2017) emphasized that interest and engagement improve comprehension outcomes, while Hong and Ganapathy (2017) noted that motivated students perform better in reading. Teachers play a crucial role in enhancing students' motivation (Lightbown Spada, 2013).

1.1.6. Inherent Ability and Extrinsic Drive to Excel—Inherent ability, driven by curiosity and intrinsic motivation, leads students to engage deeply in reading (Ahmadi, 2016; Cherry, 2020). Extrinsic drive, fueled by competition and recognition, also influences reading motivation (Komiya, 2013; Taboada Barber Klada, 2015). Extrinsic academic skills, including compliance and the desire for good grades, drive students to perform better in reading (Pangestika, 2018; Chinappi, 2015).

1.1.7. Test Compliance and Social Sharing—Test compliance refers to students' motivation to excel in standardized tests, often driven by grades (Desta, 2020). Social sharing, defined by Pangestika (2018), enhances learning through interaction with peers and teachers. Camacho-Minuche et al. (2021) and Gillies (2016) highlighted the benefits of cooperative learning, particularly in large classrooms.

1.2. Synthesis—Several types of research mentioned above have shown that interaction be-

tween teachers and students is influential to the educational eagerness of the students. Current empirical research has shown that more remarkable results in terms of students' willingness to learn English were achieved by instructional capability. For instance, a study by Wegner et al. (2014) found that when teachers use various teaching techniques in the classroom, students become more active and engaged in the learning process and learn better. According to Khalid et al. (2013), pupils always recall what they did rather than what they memorized when teachers' instructional capabilities are used in the classroom. According to this, Ridwan et al. (2019) made it evident that teachers should employ instructional tactics to create an active classroom since active students will be present in an active class. Hence, the above literature review helped the researcher establish the conceptual and theoretical framework by explicitly discussing the nature of variables, the choice of population, and the method used to answer the identified research objectives.

1.3. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework—The current study is anchored on the Atkinson and McClelland (1953) achievement motivation theory, which explains the influence of the motive to achieve and the motive to avoid failure in a situation where performance is evaluated against some standard of excellence. It focuses primarily on resolving the conflict between two opposing tendencies inherent in any achievement-oriented activity. The tendency to undertake an activity is the product of motive, expectancy, and incentive. Tendency to achieve success is the product of the motive or need, the strength of expectancy that success will be the consequence of a particular activity, and the incentive value of success at that specific activity. In this study, reading motivation is the strong desire to meet reasonable standards and the motive to avoid failure or to continue despite failure. In education, where tasks and workloads are taxing, the motive to achieve compels the

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

learner to do the intended performance, leading to achieving the desired results. Their motivation predicts students' interest and persistence in reading.

Also, Self-Determination Theory (SDT) by Edward Deci and Richard Ryan relates to human motivation and achievement. This theory focuses on creating a learning environment that encourages the development of individual intrinsic motivation. According to SDT, when the individual is motivated, they intend to accomplish a task and undertake goal-oriented behavior to attain the objective. Accordingly, students' self-determination within the teaching and learning environment was associated with positive outcomes, such as academic performance. Intrinsically motivated students will be inclined to emphasize their effort and engagement in learning and school activities. Therefore, this study will emphasize that students who receive sufficient emotional support from their families will be motivated if they feel that the learning environment encourages and assists them in learning mathematics. Also, Tenenbaum (2018) proposed that the more parent and teacher-perceived parental academic support in the student's education, the higher the student's math achievement scores. Likewise, Wilder (2014) postulated that parent-school involvement is an essential contributor to student academic success. Similarly, Wang and Sheikh-

Khalil (2014) found that parental academic support is associated with GPA positively through enhancing educational engagement. As shown in Figure 1, the study is composed of two variables. The independent variable is the home-school partnership or extent of the emotional and physical presence of the parents, and being consistently dependable for the students in times of their academic needs. The measures of home-school partnership according to Cadosales et al. (2017) are time students spend with their parents or the quality time spent by the parents with their children in relation to academic tasks; parent's involvement in school or the activities and behaviors parents engage in at school, such as attending parent-teacher conferences and attending school events; and parent's ways of discipline or the methods utilized by the parents to reinforce a particular behavior of a child. The dependent variable is reading skills or the abilities that pertain to a person's capacity to read, comprehend, interpret and decode written language and texts. According to Pangestika (2018) the measures of reading skills are inherent ability or the curiosity for challenge items, extrinsic drive to excel or the desire of students in improving their second language

reading ability, extrinsic academic compliance or the extent of compliance and consciousness for grades, test compliance or the students' desire in gaining scores on English standardized test, and social sharing or the extent of students' sharing of their experiences with others.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—The primary objective of this study was to look into the influence of home-school partnerships on the reading skills of the learners in Bangoy District, Davao City. Specifically, the study has the following objectives:

- (1) What is the extent of home-school partnership in terms of
 - (1) Time Spend with Parents;
 - (2) Parents' Involvement in School; and
 - (3) Parents' Ways of Discipline?
- (2) What is the extent of reading skills of learners in terms of:
 - (1) Inherent Ability;
 - (2) Extrinsic Drive to Excel;
 - (3) Extrinsic Academic Skills;
 - (4) Test Compliance; and
 - (5) Social Sharing?
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between home-school partnership and learners' reading skills in Bangoy District, Davao City?
- (4) Which domain of home-school partnership significantly influences the reading skills of learners in Bangoy District, Davao City?

1.5. Hypothesis—The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance: H01: There is no significant relationship between home-school partnership and learners' reading skills in Bangoy District, Davao City. H02: None of the home-school partnership domains significantly influence learners' reading skills in Bangoy District, Davao City.

1.6. Significance of the Study—Thus, considering this cited problem situation, the researcher finds it timely to propose this study. This also brought the necessity for the researcher to look into the relationship between the home-school partnership and learners' reading skills. The researcher hopes that this study may be beneficial to identified sectors of the academe. This includes the Department of Education (DepEd), School administrators, teachers, and students. The Department of Education, DepEd, would benefit from the findings of this study because they can provide them with perspective on how to address the needs

of learners. This can also provide students with insight on how to support teachers. The study of educational zeal is crucial because it may give policymakers a foundation for creating curricula that could sustain higher levels of learner self-regulated learning. School Administrators. This study may offer information to school administrators so they may decide what programs are required to provide resources to help children catch up, as most students are expected to suffer anxiety in studying at some time this school year. From there, it will be possible to detect which students could require further support, and they might get in touch with students who have learning difficulties and let students and families self-identify as needing extra assistance. Teachers. The findings are essential to the teaching profession because they suggest future evidence-based interventions that can be implemented regarding the positive effect of parental academic support on the motivation towards reading among students. The knowledge

attained about influence of vocabulary learning strategy on the reading motivation can be extended to future students as well as other teachers. For instance, programs for helping students utilize vocabulary learning strategy can be incorporated. These essential programs could serve as an intervention as well as a preventative measure for possible undesirable consequences of poor reading habits. Students. This study could benefit students because it helps them learn to make sense of not only the world around them but also people, building social-emotional skills and, of course, imagination. With the ability to use vocabulary learning strategies, students will have higher vocabulary skills, increased success with spelling, and a deeper understanding of the world around them. Future Researchers. Other researchers would benefit from the results of this study because the findings may provide a framework and model for future research in the context of home-school partnerships and learners' reading skills. For a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms were defined operationally: The home-school partnership was conceptually defined as the emotional and physical presence of the parents and their consistent dependableness for the students in times of their academic needs. This study refers to the independent variable being described in terms of time students spend with their parents, parents' involvement in school, and parents' ways of discipline. Reading Skills were conceptually defined as the abilities that pertain to a person's capacity to read, comprehend, interpret, and decode written language and texts. In this study, the dependent variable was described in terms of the following indicators: inherent ability, extrinsic drive to excel, extrinsic academic skills, test compliance, and social sharing.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, we will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) was expressly utilized to enhance the overall quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—The study employed a non-experimental design utilizing the descriptive correlation technique of research, which is designed to gather data, ideas, facts, and information related to the study. Quantitative research deals with numbers, logic, and objective stances. It focuses on numeric and unchanging data and detailed, convergent reasoning, generating a variety of ideas about a research problem (Babbie et al. 2010). According to Myers and Well (2013), correlated design examines how the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes cause-and-effect relationships between variables. It enabled the researcher to observe two variables at a point in time and helped describe the relationship of the factors of both variables. Moreover, the study also looked into the relationship between two variables— Home-school partnership and learners' reading skills in Bangoy District, Davao City. The study investigated which domains of home-school partnership significantly

influence learners’ reading skills in Bangoy District, Davao City.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—The study’s respondents were elementary school teachers in Bangoy District, Davao City. The 120 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique in this study. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. According to Shi (2015), in stratified random sampling, or stratification, the strata are formed based on members’ shared attributes or characteristics, such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling is appropriate in this study because there is heterogeneity in a population that can be classified with ancillary information. This study implemented specific inclusion criteria to determine the study’s respondents. The primary consideration of this study is to select respondents who can provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, only those permanent-regular teachers in Bangoy District, Davao City, those who were

not subjected to any administrative or criminal cases, and who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions. Thus, it did not consider the gender and socio-economic status of the teachers.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—The study employed the adapted questionnaires drafted to fit the context of the respondents of this study. The instrument was divided into two parts. The first part was about the home-school partnership, which was distributed among the three indicators: time students spend with their parents, parents’ involvement in school, and parents’ ways of discipline. The reliability of the original scale obtained a Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.976. In answering the questionnaire, the respondents made use of the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of home-school partnership, the researcher made use of the range of means, description, and interpretations as presented below:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The home-school partnership is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The home-school partnership is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The home-school partnership is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The home-school partnership is seldom observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The home-school partnership is never observed.

The second part concerned learners’ reading skills in Bangoy District, Davao City. This questionnaire was adapted from Komiyama’s (2013) Motivation for Reading English Questionnaire (MREQ), which indicated inherent ability, extrinsic drive to excel, extrinsic academic skills,

test compliance, and social sharing. The questionnaire underwent pilot testing and obtained an alpha coefficient of 0.955, suggesting that the items had high internal consistency. The instrument made use of a 5-point Likert scale that was determined based on the following range of

mean:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The reading skills of learners are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The reading skills of learners are oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The reading skills of learners are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The reading skills of learners are seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The reading skills of learners are never manifested.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The researcher underwent steps in conducting the study after the validation of the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured permission to conduct the study and the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the principals of the elementary public schools in Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. The researcher distributed the research instrument to the respondents after the study was approved. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. For the administration of the questionnaire, the study was done in the fourth quarter of the school year 2022-2023. More so, the study respondents were given enough testing time to finish the questionnaires. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the questionnaire was retrieved, the scores of each respondent were tallied to organize the data per indicator. After that, each score was

subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. *Ethical Considerations* – The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study, following the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires with supporting authors were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study. Informed Consent. The researcher asked for the permission of respondents through written informed consent. They were properly informed about the purpose of the study, and ample explanations were given to them so that they could better understand the reason for their participation and choose whether to participate or not. It was made clear that respondents’ involvement in the study was voluntary. If ever they refused to participate, they were not forced by the researcher. Besides, the researcher was cautious in ensuring the respondents’ psychological well-being. Written permission was secured from the respondents. The researcher informed the respondents that the study aimed to conduct a study on the factors that hinder/promote learners’ reading skills as determined by home-partnership and may

contribute to the enhancement. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The study's respondents are teachers, so they are considered not vulnerable since all of them are of legal age, and they are considered not vulnerable psychologically. The researcher emphasized that the survey was set at the respondents' convenience. Also, the researcher protected the confidentiality of the information disclosed. Privacy and Confidentiality. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2012, wherein the researcher assured that the data could not be traced back to the respondents, who were the real source of information, to protect the identities of the participants. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the consent of the respondents. Thus, to ensure that no personal data would be exposed, access was limited to the researcher alone. To protect the privacy of the respondents, it was assured that the researcher was the only person who could access the data on the survey. After the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently disposed of all the survey questionnaires and deleted the data results to ensure that data could not be traced back to the respondents, who were the real source of information. Risk, Benefits, and Safety - In administering the survey questionnaires, the researcher fully disclosed to the respondents the nature of their participation and thoroughly and properly explained the purpose and benefits of the study and the confidentiality of their responses as stated in the survey questionnaire. Without restrictions, the respondents could ask questions related to the study. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were not subjected to harm in any way whatsoever. Moreover, the questionnaire used in this study did not contain any degrading or unacceptable statements offensive to the study's respondents. Likewise, this study is designed purely to collect academic information related to the study, and they were not asked for personal information. To minimize inconvenience, the researcher ensured that the respondents were given ample time to answer the survey questionnaire. The respondents were given the freedom not to answer questions that made them feel any psychological or emotional distress, and they would be free to withdraw as respondents to the study if they felt that they could not discuss the information that was being asked of them. Justice. To avoid impartiality in choosing the respondents, the researcher regarded all respondents equally regardless of whether they would be respondents in the survey. The researcher was not prejudiced in selecting the study respondents—anybody who fit the qualifications of being permanent-regular teachers in the purposively selected schools. During the study, the researcher respected the respondents by interrupting their routine as little as possible. To compensate for the time spent during data gathering, the researcher gave tokens of appreciation to the respondents. This token was an assortment of souvenirs. The tokens were sent via courier, sealed carefully in a package. Also, each token was sanitized before being sent to your doorstep. Transparency. To provide transparency in this study, any communication concerning the research was done honestly and openly. To safeguard the respondents' welfare, the researcher correctly implemented the methods discussed in this study. All the necessary documents that supported the data analysis were included. Notably, the researcher described the extent of the respondents' involvement in this study and shared how the researcher maintained objectivity in analyzing data and presenting the results of the study. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that other factors like the conflict of interest did not influence the respondents' responses. The study's findings could be accessed by the respondent's parents and school administrators of the participating schools because the information would be made available as long as they followed proper protocol to protect the anonymity of the respondents. The researcher

also acknowledged the effort of every person who contributed to the success of the study, the Division of Davao City was given a furnished copy of the research results so that the respondents could access them and use them for learning and further study. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher engaged the respondents in a conducive environment and learning materials, which were ample and available in the study and were done within the time set by the researcher. The accuracy of gathering data from the respondents was ensured by adequately encoding the respondents' ratings during the day when the researcher was not too tired to do them to avoid errors in encoding. Also, the analysis and results were proficient and aligned, serving as a primary basis for adequacy. Community Involvement. It was good practice to involve the community during every phase of research, from planning to reporting. Hence, the researcher planned to share the findings generated with the community, and community involvement was accorded primacy in making decisions about the research agenda, appropriate methods to apply in their

context, and use of the results or findings. The findings of this study would then be shared with the community through gatherings, fora, and conferences.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the home-school partnership and learners' reading skills in Bangoy District, Davao City. It was also used to supply the answer for objectives 1 and 2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. It was used in this study to assess the significant relationship between independent (home-school partnership) and dependent (reading skills of learners) variables. It is a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it is usually denoted by r . This was used to supply the answer for objective 3. Multiple linear regression was applied to evaluate which domains of home-school partnership significantly influence the reading skills of learners in Bangoy District, Davao City. This was used to supply the answer for objective 4.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the study's objectives, as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of home-school partnership and reading skills in Bangoy District, Davao City; the significant relationship between home-school partnership and reading skills in Bangoy District, Davao City; and the domains of home-school partnership significantly influence the reading skills in Bangoy District, Davao City.

3.1. Home-School Partnership in Bangoy District, Davao City—

3.1.1. *Time Students Spend with their Parents*—Table 1 shows that the home-school partnership in terms of time students spend with their parents was assessed by the respondents as extensive with a category mean of 3.43, interpreted as oftentimes observed. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 2.99 to 3.91. On the one hand, the item. Studying difficult lessons at home has a mean rating of 2.99, de-

scribed as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed by respondents. On the other hand, the item Needing motivation reflects a mean of 3.91, which is described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. This implies that the respondents often observe the quality time spent by the parents with their children concerning academic tasks. This is congruent with the view of Parker and Wang (2013) that parents who think they spend the right amount of time with their children are about three times

as likely as parents stating that they spend little time with their children to say their parenting job is excellent. The result supports the idea of Garcia and Thornton (2014) that students develop a lifelong love of learning and acquire the home support and knowledge they need to finish their assignments when parents are engaged in their children’s school lives.

Table 1. Home-School Partnership in Terms of Time Students Spend with their Parents

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Doing my homework.	3.32	Moderately Extensive
Having difficulties in school.	3.81	Extensive
Finding it challenging to understand the world.	3.46	Extensive
Have personal problems.	3.71	Moderately Extensive
Studying difficult lessons at home.	2.99	Moderately Extensive
Needing tutorial.	3.07	Moderately Extensive
Buying materials needed in the performance tasks.	3.52	Extensive
Needing encouragement.	3.21	Moderately Extensive
Needing motivation.	3.91	Extensive
Needing advice.	3.34	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.43	Extensive

3.1.2. *Parents Involvement in School*—Results in Table 2 show that parents’ involvement in school got an extensive category mean rating of 3.40, which means that this domain of home-school partnership in Bangoy District in Davao City is oftentimes observed by the teachers. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 2.87 to 3.88. The item Having homeroom meet-

ings reflects a mean rating of 2.87, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as an item sometimes observed by the respondents. Meanwhile, the item Needing to get report card shows a rating of 3.88, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes observed by the respondents in Bangoy District, Davao City.

This implies that the activities and behaviors parents engage in at school, such as attending parent-teacher conferences and attending school events, are oftentimes observed in Bangoy District, Davao City. This agrees with the view of Child Trends (2013) that students with parents who are involved in their school tend to have better academic performance. These students perform better in school compared to

students with parents who are not involved in their school. Similarly, this supports the idea of Pinantoan (2013) that parents should be aware of the activities their children participate in and praise them whenever they earn an achievement for their children’s hard work to pay off.

3.1.3. *Parents’ Ways of Discipline*—Results in Table 3 show that parents’ ways of discipline got an extensive category mean rating

Table 2. Home-School Partnership in Terms of Parent Involvement in School

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Having activities in school that need their presence.	3.71	Moderately Extensive
Having homeroom meetings.	2.87	Extensive
Having family days in school.	3.07	Extensive
Having consultations with teachers.	3.52	Moderately Extensive
Having consulted the parents due to failing grades.	3.36	Moderately Extensive
Parents’ attention was called due to misbehavior in class.	3.73	Moderately Extensive
Calling the attention of parents when learners fail to submit requirements on time.	2.99	Extensive
Joining community extension services.	3.14	Moderately Extensive
Participating in school programs.	3.77	Extensive
Needing to get a report card.	3.88	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.40	Extensive

of 3.41, which means that this domain of home-school partnership in Bangoy District in Davao City is oftentimes observed by the teachers. The table further reveals that the mean rating of the items ranges from 2.65 to 4.02. It is noteworthy that the item Being corrected when bullying

somebody has a mean rating of 2.65, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as the item is sometimes observed, while the item Being disciplined when having failing grades has a mean rating of 4.02, described as extensive and interpreted as item oftentimes observed.

This means that the methods the parents utilize to reinforce a child’s particular behavior are often observed in Bangoy District, Davao City. This agrees with Cadosales et al. (2017) that the parenting style employed by the parents affects their relationship with their children. Additionally, the result supports Adibsereshki et al. (2015) proposition that how parents discipline their children can influence their behavior in school. Positive reinforcement is considered a complex exercise. This is because it demands the teacher’s talent, skills, energy, and ability to manage a classroom. After all, it directly deals with the behaviors of learners.

3.1.4. Summary of home-school partnership in Bangoy District in Davao City—It shows that the overall mean of home-school partnership is 3.41, which is described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. More so, home-school partnership in terms of time spent with their parents acquired the highest mean score of 3.43, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. In contrast, home-school partnerships in terms of parents’ involvement in school got the lowest mean score of 3.40, described as extensive and interpreted as frequently observed.

Table 3. Home-School Partnership in Terms of Parents’ Ways of Discipline

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Being corrected when misbehaving in school.	3.45	Moderately Extensive
Assisted when they do not study lessons.	3.01	Extensive
Being restricted when playing computer games.	3.46	Extensive
Being told when texting all the time.	3.39	Moderately Extensive
Being corrected when bullying somebody.	2.65	Moderately Extensive
Being disciplined when failing to do household chores.	3.35	Moderately Extensive
Being called when going home late.	3.92	Extensive
Being disciplined when having failing grades.	4.02	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.41	Extensive

Table 4. Summary of Home-School Partnership in Bangoy District, Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Time Students Spend with their Parents	3.43	Extensive
Parents’ Involvement in School	3.40	Extensive
Parents’ Ways of Discipline	3.41	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.41	Extensive

The extensive rating on home-school partnership means that the emotional and physical presence of the parents and being consistently dependable for the students in times of their academic needs is oftentimes observed in Bangoy District, Davao City. This result is congruent with Durisic and Bunijevac’s (2017) assertion that home-school partnership is an effective tool that encourages children’s and adolescents’ achievement in many ways. Moreover, the result agrees with Delgado (2020) that parents’

involvement in school activities helps boost the students’ self-esteem by knowing that their parents support them. Finally, parenting styles contribute to the student’s achievement.

3.2. *Reading Skills of Learners in Bangoy District, Davao City—*

3.2.1. *Inherent Ability—*This domain reveals a category mean of 3.69, described as extensive. In particular, the mean ratings in this category range from 3.35 to 4.04.

The item, Liking it when the topic of an English reading makes me think a little more, has a mean of 3.35, is described as moderately extensive, and is sometimes interpreted as an item manifested. Moreover, the item Reading diffi-

cult English material more efficiently when the assignment is interesting has a mean of 4.04, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested. This finding supports Ahmadi’s (2016) view that intrinsically

Table 5. Reading Skills of Learners in Terms of Inherent Ability

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Liking to read English to learn something new about people and things that interest me.	3.81	Extensive
Feeling happy when I read about something interesting in English.	3.39	Moderately Extensive
Reading about new things in English.	3.85	Extensive
Reading more about it in English when my teacher or friends tell me something interesting.	3.73	Extensive
Enjoying reading in English to learn what is going on in the U.S. and the world.	3.65	Extensive
Reading a lot of interesting things in English.	3.66	Extensive
Having fun while reading about something I like in English.	3.71	Extensive
It is hard for me to stop reading in English when the topic is interesting.	3.63	Extensive
Enjoying reading good, long stories in English.	3.72	Extensive
Losing track of time when I am reading about an interesting topic in English.	3.62	Extensive
Being willing to read difficult English materials when the topic is interesting.	3.61	Extensive
Enjoying reading when I learn complex ideas from English materials.	3.69	Extensive
Liking it when the topic of an English reading makes me think a little more.	3.35	Moderately Extensive
Liking challenging myself while reading in English.	3.72	Extensive
Liking hard, challenging English readings.	3.79	Extensive
Reading difficult English material more easily when the assignment is interesting.	4.04	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.69	Extensive

motivated students are willing to learn and are highly interested in learning activities even without any reward because they come from their desire. Also, Cherry (2020) viewed an intrinsically motivated person as someone who moves to act on something they want to do, even just for fun or challenge, which means intrinsic motivation comes from within itself, usually driven by personal desire.

3.2.2. *Extrinsic Drive To Excel*—This domain on the extrinsic drive to Excel garners a mean category of 3.66, described as extensive. In particular, the means of the items in this category range from 3.34 to 3.94. Adding on, the item on Thinking about how well I read

compared to others when I read shows a mean of 3.34, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as an item sometimes manifested. Meanwhile, the item, Wanting to be the best at reading, has a mean of 3.94, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested by the respondents in Bangoy District, Davao City. This implies that learners driven by extrinsic motivation tend to exhibit greater persistence in their efforts to excel in reading. This persistence can be instrumental in tackling complex literary works and expanding their vocabulary and comprehension skills. This finding supports the proposition of Steinmayr et al. (2019), who expressed that the extrinsic

drive to excel energizes and directs behavior toward achievement and, therefore, is known to be an important determinant of academic success.

Table 6. Reading Skills of Learners in Terms of Extrinsic Drive To Excel

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Being willing to work hard to read better than my friends.	3.62	Extensive
Being the only student who knows an answer about something we read.	3.62	Extensive
Trying to get more answers correct than my classmates when I complete reading assignments for class.	3.69	Extensive
Finishing my reading assignments before other students when I read.	3.39	Moderately Extensive
Wanting to be the best at reading.	3.94	Extensive
Wanting to read more materials when some classmates read better than me.	3.69	Extensive
Thinking about how well I read compared to others when I read.	3.34	Moderately Extensive
Practicing reading because I want a higher reading score than my friends and classmates on tests.	3.76	Extensive
Liking my teacher to say that I read well.	3.71	Extensive
Liking my friends to tell me that I am a good reader.	3.79	Extensive
Liking it when my teacher asks me to read aloud in class.	3.62	Extensive
Liking to get positive comments about my reading.	3.66	Extensive
Practicing reading because I feel good when answering teachers' questions correctly.	3.39	Moderately Extensive
Feeling happy when my friends ask me for help with their reading assignments.	3.72	Extensive
Being happy when someone knows about my ability in Reading.	3.81	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.65	Extensive

High-level learners may receive recognition for their reading achievements through extrinsic motivators. This recognition can boost their self-esteem and encourage them to excel further, creating a cycle of improvement. Likewise, Sarangi (2015) asserted that the extrinsic drive to excel is a primary condition to achieve something. Learners may leverage their intrinsic skills and talents in reading when coupled with extrinsic motivation. This can lead to accelerated skill development, enabling them to explore advanced literary genres and texts.

3.2.3. *Extrinsic Academic Skills*—This domain has a category mean of 3.71, described as extensive. The item in this category obtained mean ratings within the range of 3.39 to 4.06. Particularly, the item I need to receive a good grade on in my English reading course has a mean rating of 3.39, is described as moderately extensive, and is sometimes interpreted as an item manifested. Meanwhile, the item, Working Harder on English Reading Assignments When They Are Graded, has a mean of 4.06, which is described as extensive and interpreted as an item that is oftentimes manifested.

Table 7. Reading Skills of Learners in Terms of Extrinsic Academic Skills

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Finding it important to finish English reading assignments on time.	3.69	Extensive
Trying to finish my English reading assignments on time.	3.72	Extensive
Doing my English reading assignments exactly as the teacher tells me to do them.	3.74	Extensive
Practicing reading in English because I need to do well in my future classes.	3.63	Extensive
It is important for me to receive a good grade in my English reading course.	3.39	Moderately Extensive
Looking forward to finding out my grades in English reading.	3.71	Extensive
Wanting to read in English to improve my grades.	3.74	Extensive
Working harder on English reading assignments when they are graded.	4.06	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.71	Extensive

The result denotes that the extent of compliance and consciousness for grades is often-times manifested by the respondents in Bangoy District, Davao City. This finding supports the proposition of Chinappi (2015) pointed out that extrinsically motivated students, due to compliance, tend to share what they read with other students, outperform other students, and aim to please their parents. In other words, extrinsic reading motivation is reading motivation because of external reasons. Extrinsic academic compliance includes the reason students read in a foreign language as the form of their responsibilities in reading classes. More so, Risinger

Meanwhile, the item, Trying to read in English because I need a good test score, has a mean of 3.71, described as extensive and interpreted as an item often manifested. This implies that students often manifest a desire to gain scores on English standardized tests. This finding supports Desta’s (2020) view that grades are a factor that can impact academic motivation in students and can even create a fear of

(2013) noted that reading motivation literature suggests that compliance is a statement of outcome and indicates the achievement of a goal identified in reading-related tasks.

3.2.4. *Test Compliance*—This domain on extrinsic test compliance garners a mean category of 3.66, which is described as extensive. In particular, the means of the items in this category range from 3.64 to 3.71. Adding on, the item on trying to read in English because I like seeing my reading score improve on tests shows a mean of 3.64, which is described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested.

failure. Grades motivate students because they are a way to determine which people in a group are objectively most intelligent.

3.2.5. *Social Sharing*—This domain has a category mean of 3.70 described as extensive. Notably, the items in this category obtained mean ratings ranging from 3.37 to 4.04. The item My friends and I like to share what we read in English has a mean of 3.37, described

Table 8. Reading Skills of Learners in Terms of Test Compliance

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Trying to read in English because I need a good score on tests.	3.71	Extensive
Trying to read in English because I like seeing my reading score improve on tests.	3.64	Extensive
Reading in English with the aim to pass in English course.	3.70	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.66	Extensive

as moderately extensive and interpreted as an item sometimes manifested. Meanwhile, the item, Trying to read in English so I can understand what my friends are talking about, has a mean rating of 4.04, described as extensive, interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested.

Table 9. Reading Skills of Learners in Terms of Social Sharing

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Enjoying telling my friends about the things I read in English materials.	3.69	Extensive
My friends and I like to share what we read in English.	3.37	Moderately Extensive
Talking with my friends about what I read in English.	3.69	Extensive
Joining class discussions about what I read in English.	3.68	Extensive
Trying to read in English so I can understand what my friends are talking about.	4.04	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.70	Extensive

The result implies that the extent of sharing of their experiences with others is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This finding supports the proposition of Camacho-Minuche, Espinosa-Celinica, and Ulehlova (2021) that social sharing can be especially beneficial for large classes in language teaching. Learners who share their reading experiences socially often gain a deeper understanding of English texts. Discussing and analyzing literature with others helps them uncover hidden nuances,

themes, and literary devices. Also, Gillies (2016) pointed out that actively participating in discussions and sharing their thoughts on English texts exposes high-level learners to a broader range of vocabulary and expressions. They can learn new words and idiomatic expressions in context.

3.2.6. *Summary of Reading Skills of Learners in Bangoy District, Davao City*—Table 10 that the extent of reading skills of learners in Bangoy District, Davao City, has an over-

all mean rating of 3.68, which is described as extensive. Adding more, results on the table show that reading skills in terms of extrinsic academic skills got the highest mean score of 3.71, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested while reading skills in terms of extrinsic drive to excel got the lowest mean score of 3.65 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested in Bangoy District, Davao City.

Table 10. Summary of Reading Skills of Learners in Bangoy District, Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Inherent Ability	3.69	Extensive
Extrinsic Drive to Excel	3.65	Extensive
Extrinsic Academic Skills	3.71	Extensive
Test Compliance	3.66	Extensive
Social Sharing	3.70	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.68	Extensive

The result means that the respondents oftentimes manifest the learner’s driving force that pulls them to engage in reading. This finding is congruent to the view of Hussain et al. (2020) that motivation is a factor that pushes learners to learn a English language. It plays a crucial role in learning achievement. Accordingly, motivated students tend to engage in learning activities that help them to learn and achieve the learning goal because they will pay attention and use the time effectively during teaching and learning in the class. Mahadi and Jafari (2012) also noted that applying several motivational strategies in learning would bring positive results to students. Likewise, Alhamdu (2015) pointed out that motivation is important in reading engagement and affects the results of reading achievement and school success.

*3.2.7. Significant Relationship Between Home-School Partnership and Reading Skills of Learners in Bangoy District, Davao City—*The results of the analysis of the relationship between home-school partnerships and learners’

reading skills are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 11 shows the relationships between home-school partnerships and learners’ reading skills in Bangoy District, Davao City. It shows that home-school collaboration has a significant positive relationship with the reading skills of learners in Bangoy District in Davao City with a p-value of .000 that is less than the .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .447, p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of the home-school partnership changes, learners’ reading skills also significantly change. Moreover, home-school partnerships in terms of time spend with their parents, parents’ involvement in school, and parents’ ways of discipline have significant positive relationships with the reading skills of learners in Bangoy District in Davao City with a p-value of .000 is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .756, p < 0.05$), ($r = .901, p < 0.05$), and ($r = .304, p < 0.05$), respectively.

Table 11. Significant Relationship Between Home-School Partnership and Reading Skills of Learners in Bangoy District, Davao City

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision
Time Students Spend with their Parents	0.756*	0.000	Reject H0
Parents' Involvement in School	0.901*	0.000	Reject H0
Parents' Ways of Discipline	0.304*	0.000	Reject H0
Overall Home-School Partnership	0.447*	0.000	Reject H0

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

Legend:

Perfect Correlation for $r = 1.00$; Strong Correlation for $0.7 \leq r \leq 1.00$; Moderate Correlation for $0.3 \leq r \leq 0.7$;

The current study findings denote that home-school partnerships foster a sense of shared responsibility for a child's education. Parents, caregivers, and teachers work together to ensure reading skills are developed in school and at home. The present finding conforms to the anchored proposition by Núñez et al. (2015) that when parents and caregivers are actively involved in their child's reading journey, they can instill a love for reading by reading together, discussing books, and providing access to a variety of reading materials. Home-school partnerships encourage the establishment of regular reading routines at home. Parents can set aside dedicated time for reading, creating a habit that reinforces the skills taught at school.

3.2.8. *Significance on the Influence of Home-School Partnership and Reading Skills of Learners in Bangoy District, Davao City*—The significance of the influence of home-school partnerships on learners' reading skills was analyzed using multiple linear regression analysis. Table 12 shows that an F-value of 7.643 with $p < 0.05$ indicates that home-school partnerships significantly influence learners' reading skills in Bangoy District, Davao City. It is, therefore,

stated that home-school partnerships predict learners' reading skills. Meanwhile, the computed adjusted R2 value of 0.332 indicates that the home-school partnership has contributed significantly to the variability of learners' reading skills by 33.20 percent of the total variability. Therefore, the difference of 66.80 percent was credited to other factors not covered in this study. In addition, the table shows that home-school partnership domains significantly influence learners' reading skills in Bangoy District, Davao City. It could be seen in the coefficient models that at 0.05 significant level, regression coefficients of 0.158 for time students spend with their parents and 0.376 for parents' involvement in school predict the reading skills of learners in Bangoy District, Davao City. This means that a unit increase in home-school partnership in terms of time students spend with their parents and parents' involvement in school corresponded to 0.158 and 0.376 units increase in reading motivation, respectively. Thus, this leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis that none of the home-school partnership domains significantly influence learners' reading skills in Bangoy District, Davao City.

Affirming that reading skills learners is a function of home-school partnership. The finding further emphasized that increasing the parental support leads to improvement of read-

ing motivation of the learners in Calinan District, Davao City. This supports the achievement motivation theory by Atkinson and McClelland (1953) which explains that the influence of mo-

Table 12. Significance of the Influence of Home-School Partnership on the Reading Skills of Learners in Bangoy District, Davao City

Home-School Partnership	B	Beta	S.E.	p-value	Decision
Time Students Spend With Their Parents	0.158**	0.237	0.049	0.002	Reject H0
Parents' Involvement in School	0.376**	0.412	0.085	0.000	Reject H0
Parents' Ways of Discipline	0.047	0.058	0.071	0.512	Accept H0
R ²	= 0.332				
F-value	= 25.499*				
p-value	= 0.000				

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

tive to achieve and the motive to avoid failure in a situation where performance is evaluated against some standard of excellence. Home-school partnerships allow for individualized support. Parents and caregivers can identify their child's reading strengths and weaknesses and

provide targeted assistance or enrichment activities. Also, parents can monitor their child's reading progress and share observations with teachers. Regular communication ensures that any reading difficulties are identified early, leading to timely interventions.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher's conclusion and recommendation. The literature supported the discussion in the first chapters, and the conclusion was by statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate which domains of home-school partnership significantly influence learners' reading skills utilizing a non-experimental quantitative design using the descriptive-correlation technique. The researcher selected the 120 elementary school teachers in Bangoy District, Davao City, as the respondents through a stratified random sampling method. The researcher used modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. Home-school partnership in Bangoy District in Davao City got an

overall mean of 3.71 with an extensive descriptive rating. Also, home-school partnership in terms of time spent with their parents, parents' involvement in school, and parents' ways of discipline obtained mean scores of 3.43, 3.40, and 3.41, respectively. The reading skills of learners in Bangoy District in Davao City have an overall mean of 3.68 and a descriptive rating of extensive. Also, the reading skills of learners in terms of inherent ability, extrinsic drive to excel, extrinsic academic skills, test compliance, and social sharing obtained mean scores of 3.69, 3.65, 3.71, 3.66, and 3.70, respectively. The home-school partnership has a significant positive relationship with the reading skills of

learners in Bangoy District in Davao City with a p-value of .000, which is less than a .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .0447$, $p < 0.05$). Also, home-school partnerships in terms of time spent with their parents, parents' involvement in school, and parents' ways of discipline have significant positive relationships with the reading skills of learners in Bangoy District in Davao City with a p-value of .000 is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .756$, $p < 0.05$), ($r = .901$, $p < 0.05$), and ($r = .304$, $p < 0.05$), respectively. Home-school partnership in terms of time students spend with their parents and parents' involvement in school significantly influenced the reading motivation of the learners, as evidenced in the F-value of 25.499 and $p < 0.05$. The r^2 value of 0.332 indicated that home-school partnerships had contributed significantly to the variability of reading skills of learners by 33.20

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were generated: Home-school partnerships in terms of time spent with their parents, parents' involvement in school, and parents' ways of discipline obtained extensive descriptive ratings. Overall, home-school partnerships in Bangoy District in Davao City were extensive, implying that the emotional and physical presence of the parents and being consistently dependable for the students in times of their academic needs were oftentimes observed. The reading skills of learners, in terms of intrinsic motivation, extrinsic drive to excel, extrinsic academic compliance, extrinsic test compliance, and extrinsic social sharing, acquired an extensive rating. Overall, the reading skills of learners in Bangoy District in Davao City were rated as extensive, denoting that the driving force that pulls them to engage in reading is often manifested. The result showed that home-school partnership has a significant positive relationship with learners' reading skills in Bangoy District in Davao City. This means that as the extent of the home-

school partnership changes, learners' reading skills in Bangoy District in Davao City also significantly change. Home-school partnership, in terms of time students spend with their parents and parents' involvement in school, significantly influenced the reading skills of learners in Bangoy District in Davao City. This affirmed that home-school partnership contributed to the improvement of learners' reading skills.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the findings and conclusions generated from the study, the researcher recommends the following: The home-school partnership was rated as extensive but may be raised to a higher status if an in-service training program for teachers may be implemented by the school administrator to enable them to develop their skills in dealing with parents and other stakeholders. This may help develop teacher-parent collaboration, especially during the distance learning approach amidst the pandemic. Through this, parents may be encouraged to continuously support their children by participating in different training and activities offered by the school to equip them with knowledge and skills on how to support their children and help them improve their academic performance at school. A school-based program for enhancing the learners' reading skills through extensive training in vocabulary learning strategies for students may be implemented. This program may be facilitated by different stakeholders, such as teachers, community leaders, and parents since it was found that parental involvement is a significant mediator of the relationship between vocabulary learning strategy and reading motivation. Similarly, Saliga's innovation, 'Easy Multiplication Using Grid,' which offers a visual and systematic approach to teaching multiplication, could serve as a model for structured educational tools that promote better understanding and retention in various subjects (Saliga, 2024). The program aligns with implementing the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 (Republic Act No. 10533). The Depart-

ment of Education adopts the enclosed Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program. The policy guideline emphasizes that teachers and parents are responsible for tracking and measuring students' progress and adjusting instruction accordingly. Hence, classroom assessment informs the learners and their parents and guardians of their progress. In addition, the study found that home-school partnerships only contributed to 33.20 percent of the total variability of reading skills of learners in Bangoy District in Davao City. Thus, the researcher recommends that other researchers conduct an explanatory study on the mediating factors that cause the relationship between home-school partnership and the reading skills of learners in Bangoy District in Davao City in a larger context may be conducted.

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